

ON TWO NEW ARITHMETIC FUNCTIONS AND THE k -POWER COMPLEMENT NUMBER SEQUENCES *

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Abstract The main purpose of this paper is to study the asymptotic property of the k -power complement numbers (where $k \geq 2$ is a fixed integer), and obtain some interesting asymptotic formulas.

Keywords: k -power complement number; Asymptotic formula; Arithmetic function.

§1. Introduction

Let $k \geq 2$ is a fixed integer, for each integer n , let $C(n)$ denotes the smallest integer such that $n \times C(n)$ is a perfect k -power, $C(n)$ is called k -power complement number of n . In problem 29 of reference [1], Professor F. Smarandache asked us to study the properties of the k -power complement number sequences. Let $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_s^{\alpha_s}$, we define two arithmetic function $D(n)$ and $I(n)$ similar to the derivative and integral function in mathematical analysis as follows:

$$D(n) = D(p_1^{\alpha_1}) D(p_2^{\alpha_2}) \cdots D(p_s^{\alpha_s}), \quad D(p^\alpha) = \alpha p^{\alpha-1}$$

and

$$I(n) = I(p_1^{\alpha_1}) I(p_2^{\alpha_2}) \cdots I(p_s^{\alpha_s}), \quad I(p^\alpha) = \frac{1}{\alpha+1} p^{\alpha+1}.$$

In this paper, we use the analytic method to study the asymptotic properties of the functions $D(n)$ and $I(n)$ for the k -power complement number sequences, and obtain some interesting asymptotic formulas. That is, we shall prove the following conclusions:

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Theorem 1. For any real number $x \geq 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n \leq x} \frac{1}{D(C(n))} \\ &= \frac{6(k-1)\zeta\left(\frac{k}{k-1}\right) \cdot x^{\frac{1}{k-1}}}{\pi^2} \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{p}{p+1} \sum_{i=1}^{k-2} \frac{1}{(k-i)p^{k-1-i} \cdot p^{\frac{i}{k-1}}} \right) \\ & \quad + O\left(x^{\frac{2k-1}{2k(k-1)} + \varepsilon}\right), \end{aligned}$$

where ε denotes any fixed positive number.

Theorem 2. For any real number $x \geq 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n \leq x} I(C(n))d(C(n)) \\ &= \frac{6\zeta(k(k+1)) \cdot x^{k+1}}{(k+1)\pi^2} \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{p}{p+1} \left(\sum_{i=2}^k \frac{p^{k+1-i}}{p^{(k+1)i}} - \frac{1}{p^{k(k+1)}} \right) \right) \\ & \quad + O\left(x^{k+\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon}\right), \end{aligned}$$

where $d(n) = \sum_{d|n} 1$ is the divisor function.

§2. Proof of the theorems

In this section, we shall complete the proof of the theorems. Let

$$f(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{D(C(n))n^s}.$$

Because $D(n)$ and $C(n)$ are all multiplicative function, so from the Euler product formula [2] and the definition of $D(n)$ and $C(n)$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} & f(s) \\ &= \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{1}{D(C(p))p^s} + \frac{1}{D(C(p^2))p^{2s}} + \cdots \right) \\ &= \prod_p \left(1 + \left(\sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \frac{1}{(k-i)p^{k-1-i} \cdot p^{is}} + \frac{1}{p^{ks}} \right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{p^{ks}} + \frac{1}{p^{2ks}} + \cdots \right) \right) \\ &= \zeta(ks) \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{1}{p^{(k-1)s}} + \sum_{i=1}^{k-2} \frac{1}{(k-i)p^{k-1-i} \cdot p^{is}} \right) \\ &= \frac{\zeta(ks)\zeta((k-1)s)}{\zeta((2k-2)s)} \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{p^{(k-1)s}}{p^{(k-1)s} + 1} \sum_{i=1}^{k-2} \frac{1}{(k-i)p^{k-1-i} \cdot p^{is}} \right), \end{aligned}$$

where $\zeta(s)$ is Riemann zeta function. Obviously, we have the inequality

$$\left| \frac{1}{D(C(n))} \right| \leq 1, \quad \left| \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{D(C(n))n^{\sigma}} \right| < \frac{1}{\sigma - \frac{1}{k-1}},$$

where $\sigma > \frac{1}{k-1}$ is the real part of s . So by Perron formula [3]

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n \leq x} \frac{a(n)}{n^{\sigma_0}} \\ &= \frac{1}{2i\pi} \int_{b-iT}^{b+iT} f(s + s_0) \frac{x^s}{s} ds + O\left(\frac{x^b B(b + \sigma_0)}{T}\right) \\ & \quad + O\left(x^{1-\sigma_0} H(2x) \min\left(1, \frac{\log x}{T}\right)\right) + O\left(x^{-\sigma_0} H(N) \min\left(1, \frac{x}{\|x\|}\right)\right), \end{aligned}$$

where N is the nearest integer to x , $\|x\| = |x - N|$. Taking $s_0 = 0$, $b = 1 + \frac{1}{k-1}$, $T = x^{1+\frac{1}{2k(k-1)}}$, $H(x) = 1$, $B(\sigma) = \frac{1}{\sigma - \frac{1}{k-1}}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n \leq x} \frac{1}{D(C(n))} \\ &= \frac{1}{2i\pi} \int_{1+\frac{1}{k-1}-iT}^{1+\frac{1}{k-1}+iT} \frac{\zeta(ks)\zeta((k-1)s)}{\zeta((2k-2)s)} R(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds \\ & \quad + O\left(x^{\frac{2k-1}{2k(k-1)}+\varepsilon}\right), \end{aligned}$$

where

$$R(s) = \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{p^{(k-1)s}}{p^{(k-1)s} + 1} \sum_{i=1}^{k-2} \frac{1}{(k-i)p^{k-1-i} \cdot p^{is}} \right).$$

To calculate the main term

$$\frac{1}{2i\pi} \int_{1+\frac{1}{k-1}-iT}^{1+\frac{1}{k-1}+iT} \frac{\zeta(ks)\zeta((k-1)s)x^s}{\zeta((2k-2)s)s} R(s) ds,$$

we move the integral line from $s = 1 + \frac{1}{k-1} \pm iT$ to $s = \frac{1}{k} + \frac{1}{2k(k-1)} \pm iT$.

This time, the function

$$f_1(s) = \frac{\zeta(ks)\zeta((k-1)s)}{\zeta((2k-2)s)} R(s) \frac{x^s}{s}$$

have a simple pole point at $s = \frac{1}{k-1}$ with residue $\frac{(k-1)\zeta(\frac{k}{k-1}) \cdot x^{\frac{1}{k-1}}}{\zeta(2)} R(\frac{1}{k-1})$.

So we have

$$\frac{1}{2i\pi} \left(\int_{1+\frac{1}{k-1}-iT}^{1+\frac{1}{k-1}+iT} + \int_{\frac{1}{k}+\frac{1}{2k(k-1)}+iT}^{\frac{1}{k}+\frac{1}{2k(k-1)}-iT} + \int_{\frac{1}{k}+\frac{1}{2k(k-1)}-iT}^{\frac{1}{k}+\frac{1}{2k(k-1)}+iT} + \int_{\frac{1}{k}+\frac{1}{2k(k-1)}+iT}^{1+\frac{1}{k-1}-iT} \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{\zeta(ks)\zeta((k-1)s)x^s}{\zeta((2k-2)s)s}R(s)ds \\
= & \frac{(k-1)\zeta\left(\frac{k}{k-1}\right) \cdot x^{\frac{1}{k-1}}}{\zeta(2)} \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{p}{p+1} \sum_{i=1}^{k-2} \frac{1}{(k-i)p^{k-1-i} \cdot p^{\frac{i}{k-1}}}\right).
\end{aligned}$$

We can easy get the estimate

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{1}{2\pi i} \left(\int_{1+\frac{1}{k-1}+iT}^{\frac{1}{k}+\frac{1}{2k(k-1)}+iT} + \int_{\frac{1}{k}+\frac{1}{2k(k-1)}-iT}^{1+\frac{1}{k-1}-iT} \right) \frac{\zeta(ks)\zeta((k-1)s)x^s}{\zeta((2k-2)s)s} R(s)ds \right| \\
\ll & \int_{\frac{1}{k}+\frac{1}{2k(k-1)}}^{1+\frac{1}{k-1}} \left| \frac{\zeta(k(\sigma+iT))\zeta((k-1)(\sigma+iT))}{\zeta((2k-2)(\sigma+iT))} R(s) \frac{x^{1+\frac{1}{k-1}}}{T} \right| d\sigma \\
\ll & \frac{x^{1+\frac{1}{k-1}}}{T} = x^{\frac{1}{k}+\frac{1}{2k(k-1)}}
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\frac{1}{k}+\frac{1}{2k(k-1)}+iT}^{\frac{1}{k}+\frac{1}{2k(k-1)}-iT} \frac{\zeta(ks)\zeta((k-1)s)x^s}{\zeta((2k-2)s)s} R(s)ds \right| \\
\ll & \int_0^T \left| \frac{\zeta\left(1+\frac{1}{2(k-1)}+ikt\right)\zeta\left(\frac{2k-1}{2k}+i(k-1)t\right) x^{\frac{1}{k}+\frac{1}{2k(k-1)}}}{\zeta\left(\frac{2k-1}{k}+i(2k-2)t\right) t} \right| dt \\
\ll & x^{\frac{1}{k}+\frac{1}{2k(k-1)}+\varepsilon}.
\end{aligned}$$

Note that $\zeta(2) = \frac{\pi^2}{6}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{n \leq x} \frac{1}{D(C(n))} &= \frac{6(k-1)\zeta\left(\frac{k}{k-1}\right) \cdot x^{\frac{1}{k-1}}}{\pi^2} \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{p}{p+1} \sum_{i=1}^{k-2} \frac{1}{(k-i)p^{k-1-i} \cdot p^{\frac{i}{k-1}}}\right) \\
&\quad + O\left(x^{\frac{2k-1}{2k(k-1)}+\varepsilon}\right).
\end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of Theorem 1.

Let

$$g(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} I(C(n))d(C(n))$$

from the definition of $I(n)$ and $C(n)$, we can also have

$$\begin{aligned}
g(s) &= \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{I(C(p))d(C(p))}{p^s} + \frac{I(C(p^2))d(C(p^2))}{p^{2s}} + \dots\right) \\
&= \prod_p \left(1 + \left(\frac{p^k}{p^s} + \frac{p^{k-1}}{p^{2s}} + \dots + \frac{p}{p^{ks}}\right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{p^{ks}} + \frac{1}{p^{2ks}} + \dots\right)\right)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \zeta(k s) \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^{ks}} + \frac{p^k}{p^s} + \frac{p^{k-1}}{p^{2s}} + \cdots + \frac{p}{p^{ks}} \right) \\ &= \frac{\zeta(k s) \zeta(s - k)}{\zeta(2s - 2k)} \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{p^{s-k}}{p^{s-k} + 1} \left(\sum_{i=2}^k \frac{p^{k+1-i}}{p^{is}} - \frac{1}{p^{ks}} \right) \right). \end{aligned}$$

Now by Perron formula [3] and the method of proving Theorem 1, we can also obtain Theorem 2.

Reference

- [1] F. Smarndache, *Only Problems, Not Solution*, Xiquan Publishing House, Chicago, 1993, pp. 26.
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- [3] Pan Chengdong and Pan Chengbiao, *Foundation of Analytic Number Theory*, Science Press, Beijing, 1997, pp. 98.